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ROR1 silencing promotes luminal B fate choice.

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We performed comparative tumor transcriptomics to identify factors important for luminal A and luminal B subtype bifurcation. We report identification of the nuclear receptor ROR1 as a mediator of subtype switching or selection for the A and B luminal subtypes.